

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR IMPROVING THE ETHNOPEDAGOGICAL CULTURE OF THE FUTURE MUSIC TEACHER

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Annotation: In this article, there are scientific discussions on the pedagogical conditions and methodology of shaping the ethnopedagogical culture of the future music teacher.

Key words: Music education, ethnopedagogy, pedagogical activity, state education standard, methodology, scientific analysis.

In modernizing the educational system implemented in our country, the problem of forming the methodological culture of the teacher who can independently design the space of his pedagogical activity comes to the fore. At the current stage, it is not possible to solve the problems of the educational process by usual methods. The school, including the additional education system, needs specialists with methodological competence. Therefore, in the last decade, methodological aspects of pedagogical education have become the focus of the pedagogical community, and today the formation of the methodological culture of a teacher-musician has become an integral part of the specialist's professional and pedagogical training, which is confirmed in the State Standard.

This means that every teacher-musician learns to study his professional activities, to understand the effectiveness of the teaching methods used, to analyze and design the results and content of music education, and also to study the initial stages of such research. he must understand the principles and principles himself.

However, the analysis of practice shows that both graduate students and experienced teachers have a low level of methodological competence. Teachers do not have a clear idea about methodology, and the concept of "methodology" is often associated with research activities in which they do not feel competent.

Thus, there is a significant contradiction between the normative requirements for a modern additional education teacher and the actual situation of the level of methodological competence of practicing teachers. Eliminating this contradiction, first of all, the system of additional professional education and training of teachers, which is the most mobile and flexible, allows to regularly adjust the professional level of working teachers according to the requirements of the day.

What is the essence of pedagogical methodology, in particular, musical pedagogy?

In 1867, K. D. Ushinsky, a classic of pedagogical thought, wrote in his book "man as a subject of education": "Pedagogy is not a science, but an art: the broadest, most complex, highest and most necessary of all arts, The art of science is based on science. As a complex and broad art, it relies on many broad and complex disciplines; as an art, it requires skill and aptitude beyond knowledge, and as an art, it is eternally attainable and never attainable.

"strives to an unattainable ideal: the ideal of a perfect person"¹. Pedagogy as an art includes not only knowledge in various fields of science and culture, but also (as a necessary condition) emotional and creative principles, the desire to improve all aspects of the pedagogical process, to educate the minds and hearts of students. These judgments are especially important for the description of pedagogy in the field of artistic activity, where it takes on the characteristics of art even more.

Methodology (literally - word - "knowledge of methods, methods of action") is a system of principles and methods of organizing and building theoretical and practical activities. In the scientific dictionary, the term "methodology" is used in several senses:

- as a teaching about the scientific method of knowing;
- as a set of methods used in some disciplines;
- as a system of principles and methods of organizing and building theoretical and practical activities.

Metodologiyaning ikki darajasi ham mavjud:

Level I - methodology as a teaching about structure, logical organization, methods of activity;

Level II-methodology as a teaching about the building principles, forms and methods of scientific knowledge. These two levels are closely related.

Pedagogical methodology is a science of methods focused on internal mechanisms, logic of action and organization of the pedagogical process.

Based on the above characteristics, scientists define the teacher's methodological culture as an important professional quality, the criteria for its formation are methodological knowledge, research skills, and a stable positive personal attitude to methodological culture as a new pedagogical value. G. H. is of special importance in the dissertation research. Valeev helps to form the methodological culture of the teacher-researcher, the need for which is "determined by the modern socio-cultural situation, where the fast and rapidly changing modern technological society requires the rapid correction of the existing ones and the development of radically new educational programs"².

Methodical culture of a music teacher, according to E. B. Abdullin, is an integral feature of the teacher's personality, which "...includes

- interest in the methodology of music education pedagogy, understanding its importance for practical activity and the personality of a music teacher;
- to have professionally oriented methodological knowledge;
- learned methods and methods of scientific-research musical-pedagogical activity and their creative application in the context of methodological analysis of literature and practical educational-research musical-pedagogical activity"³.

¹ Ушинский К.Д. Человек как предмет воспитания. — М., 1867.

² Валеев Г.Х. Формирование методологической культуры учителя-исследователя: Автореф. дис. ... д-ра пед. наук. Уфа, 2001.

³ Методология педагогики музыкального образования : учебник для студ. высш. пед. учеб. заведений / Э.Б. Абдуллин, Е.В. Николаева, Б. М.Целковников и др.; под ред. Э.Б.Абдуллина. — 2-е изд., испр. и доп. — М. : Издательский центр «Академия», 2006. — 272 с.

All disciplines of professional training and retraining of teachers should be directed to a certain extent to the formation of methodological culture. This process is most effectively carried out with a harmonious combination of general cultural, general scientific, professional and pedagogical training, as well as common elements of skills for working with modern media. Thus, in the conditions of the modern information society, the mastering of "non-professional components" (the term of G. Kh. Valeeva), which is understood as knowledge of the Internet and foreign languages, databases and data banks, and the use of computer technologies, is of particular importance⁴.

This approach is also observed in the organization of the educational process at our IDPO, which is in the organization of educational content (inclusion of subjects or methodical sections in curricula and work programs), as well as in the improvement of teaching forms (didactic introduction of active, problematic, dialogic forms of teaching methods such as games, modeling, micro-teaching) is manifested.. discussions, creation and protection of creative projects, writing scientific works, etc.).

It is known that the methodological base of musical education, like any other field of activity, is knowledge at the general scientific level (philosophy as a means of determining the value-semantic bases, priorities and functions of musical art, education and upbringing);

- in particular, scientific (musicology, general and musical psychology and pedagogy, youth physiology, acoustics);
- technological level (implementation of educational or pedagogical research program, use of innovative technologies in teaching, having modern work methods and forms).

Musical psychology, which is the main scientific basis for the formation of a modern individual methodology of teaching musical performance, occupies a special place in the professional training of an instrumentalist teacher (this issue is defined by the author as "the synthesis of psychological, pedagogical and musical-practical knowledge for the future teacher- as the central task of the methodical training of musicians" was considered in detail in the article).

However, a crucial, indispensable condition for the formation of the art teacher's methodological culture is the inclusion of a special course devoted to this problem. It is clear that this complex pedagogical problem cannot be fully solved in the small number of hours allocated to this discipline. Therefore, we believe that the main goal of this course is to form in the listeners, first of all, a positive attitude to the methodology of musical education, a desire for professional self-improvement in this direction, as well as basic, initial knowledge, skills in this field and we will consider equipping with skills that the teacher will need in his further methodological development.

The scope of methodological knowledge acquired in this course is more of an introduction to the methodology of music education pedagogy and therefore its scope is limited. It includes: theoretical knowledge on the basics of methodology - definitions, basic concepts, approaches, methods, levels of methodology; in the modern model of education, special attention is paid to the perceived competence.

⁴ Валеев Г.Х. Формирование методологической культуры учителя-исследователя: Автореф. дис. ... д-ра пед. наук. Уфа, 2001.

A very important task is to master specific terminology by the listeners, to understand and clarify the meaning of some words and concepts related to the analyzed problem. Thus, clarifying similar and seemingly synonymous terms such as "methodology" and "methodology", "competency" and "competence", "pedagogical research" and "pedagogical experiment", "goals" and "tasks" and differentiate discussions, debates, dialogic, problem-based and other forms of education, based on the activities of the listeners themselves. Note that in a certain field (in our case, in the field of pedagogical methodology), knowledge of language and terminology is directly related to thinking, understanding the mechanisms and laws of the studied processes, and therefore the professional culture in general, including the teacher - is the main basis for forming the musician's stylistic culture.

It is known that new theoretical knowledge is fully mastered only in the process of working in their intellectual and practical activities. Accordingly, the course includes many practical exercises conducted in the computer class based on the students' own educational or methodical written work materials (abstract, course work, explanatory letter to the work program, etc.), as well as specific materials of other scientific works. kept in you. During these trainings held in the form of an individual group, special attention was paid to mastering the tools of pedagogical research, developing conceptual and categorical thinking, and reflexive and analytical abilities of the listener. At the same time, several tasks were solved at the same time:

- ❖ to get acquainted with the specific features of the teacher's research activity:
- ❖ with methodology and methodology, pedagogical research methods and their classification; with the concept of "scientific research apparatus" and its components;
- ❖ with the principles of design, implementation and design of pedagogical research results;
- ❖ to study the specific features of different levels, genres and types of scientific and educational-methodological work of the teacher-researcher (review, report, Abstract, article, methodological recommendations, author's program, etc.);
- ❖ with the rules of designing working texts (including citations, bibliography), compliance with ethical standards, respect for copyright (no plagiarism);
- ❖ improvement of "professional" skills of intellectual activity:
- ❖ computer technologies, Word program services, use of the Internet, databases and electronic libraries, skills of working with texts, analysis and summarization of scientific literature data, etc.

In conclusion, we emphasize once again that the relevance and relevance of the problem of forming the methodical culture of a music teacher, from the point of view of restructuring the entire education system and determining the place and place of art pedagogy in it.

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